

README_SalGlideData

The following is a written description of all raw data associated with a manuscript published in the Journal of Experimental Biology: Aerial maneuvering by plethodontid salamanders spanning an arboreality gradient. This data was collected using the vertical wind tunnel (MIDIMASTER Eco, Siemens) in the Animal Flight lab at U.C. Berkeley in December of 2018 and 2019 with approval from the Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee.

Data was analyzed and should be viewed in the order that it is described below (4 total folders of data starting with “Point-Tracking_Pixels” and ending with “Final Data Variables”). The file names inside these folders can all be deciphered following this general scheme:

“Camera view1_Camera view 2_Salamander #_s0001_Trial #”

(e.g. FRNT_TOPP_AV21_s0001_tT03 represents the Front and Top camera views of *Aneides vagrans* individual number 21 during the 3rd trial of that salamander).

1) Folder Name: **Point-Tracking_Pixels**

This folder contains all of the raw x,y position data accumulated from tracking the center of mass (COM) and the head of the salamanders using DLTdv software (version 7, Hedrick, 2018; available from <http://biomech.web.unc.edu/dltdv/>). The units are in pixels at this stage.

Subfolders: AV21, AV22, AV23, AV24, AV25, and Calibration

These subfolders contain the point-tracking data from the five (N=5) *Aneides vagrans* with each folder named after the individual it describes (plus one folder for calibration videos).

Sub-subfolders: Trial #

Each individual salamander’s subfolder contains several additional subfolders, one for each useful trial in the vertical wind tunnel. The excel/csv files of the point-tracked pixel positions of the COM and head are in each trial sub-subfolder.

2) Folder Name: **Unsmoothed Position Data**

This folder contains all of the raw x,y,z position data converted from the original pixel position data in the folder described above. Although converted, position data has not been smoothed to account for human/software-error when point-tracking.

Subfolders: Unsmoothed.csv, Unsmoothed.xls

These subfolders differ only in file-type and contain spreadsheets of position data.

3) Folder Name: **Smoothed Position, Velocity, and Acceleration**

This folder contains all of the position data from the folder described above, but that data is now smoothed using a cubic spline. In addition, the files in this folder also contain the velocity and acceleration on the XYZ axes calculated from the smoothed position data.

4) Folder Name: **Final Data Variables**

This folder contains all of the glide angles, body angles, headings, and horizontal accelerations/velocities calculated from the smoothed position data above.

Subfolders: Final_Data_Variables_COM and Final_Data_Variables_Head

These subfolders contain the same variables for the same trials, but were calculated using different points on the salamander. The folder ending in “COM” contains all variables calculated using ONLY the position of the center of mass, not the head. The folder ending in “Head” contains all variables calculated using BOTH the position of the COM and the position of the Head, hence why the folder ending in “Head” includes columns of data for Heading and Body Angle, which cannot be calculated if tracking only one point on the animal.

All Matlab code used to generate this data has been submitted and can be navigated starting with the PDF titled "README_Matlab_Explanations"

Proceed to **README_Matlab_Explanations** and the zipped folder "Salamander Glide Code".